

The Impact of the internship program on the professional and personal development of Bop HTAW Education Empowerment Program (BHEEP)'s graduates in MNEC

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Abstract

This study aims to evaluate the impact of an internship program on the professional and personal development of Bop Htaw Education Empowerment Program (BHEEP) graduates which was established by an ethnic-based education provider (Mon National Education Committee) located in Southeast Myanmar. There were 51 internship alumni who have studied at BHEEP's two-year English program and teacher training had participated in this study. This study has identified three research questions such as identifying the knowledge background and rationale engagement of BHEEP students in internship programs at MNEC, the impacts of internship programs on professional as well as personal growth and skills of the BHEEP students and alumni, the strengths and weaknesses of the internship programs existing in MNEC, and the improved strategies to support the internship staff's professional growth and skills of the BHEEP alumni and future students. Based on the research questions the survey questions have been structured into 4 parts including the 36 closed-ended questions, 4- points Likert scale has been assessed to identify the six parts, demographic information, the reason for participating in doing an internship, assessment of data associated to professional and personal growth and skills. Quantitative and qualitative data study has been carried out in this study as well as the focus group discussion. The demographic information and central tendencies of the response have been analysis descriptively. This study used scale measurement analysis to check the distribution normality and reliabilities of the questionnaire. The result showed a positive impact of the internship program on the internship participation to improve their professional growth, skills, and personal capabilities.

Keywords: Education, personal development, Bop, HTAW, BHEEP, MNEC

Introduction

This study presents the Mon National Education Committee (MNEC) higher education internship program. MNEC is an organization that has been providing Education service for local youth at Mon community in the southeast Myanmar including basic education and higher education services. MNEC is administrating educational service to both basic and higher education program. There are 142 schools, over 13000 students, approximately 800 teachers are teaching at different school and about 70 staffs working as operational staffs at both central level and township level office. This work-based Capstone Project has studied about the MNEC higher education program internship which aims to identify the impact of the MNEC's internship on professional and personal development of Bop Htaw Education Empowerment Program (BHEEP)' alumni. BHEEP is an

English language skill upgrading emphasis in teaching English to speaker of other language program that is established by the Mon National Education Committee organization where is located in Mawlamyine, Mon State, Myanmar. It is an English program for young adult from Mon Community, Southern Myanmar. After two-year learning at classroom based, there will be 2 years internship at the local community school and Mon Education organization office.

Rationale

Now a day, labor market has been changing rapidly in Mon Community. It is quite challenging for Mon youth to work in an appropriate working field in the local community and home country. It is a prevalent social concern that students didn't have a chance to learn problem-solving and useful job

skills in Myanmar Higher education. Higher Education program is where students learn skills to do things in life so the institutions are needed to provide relevant job skills before they enter the job market. Graduated students should be trained and get more chances to explore more about the outside world's imagination to prepare them to be ready in the field of career which is most suitable for them. Additionally, the graduates should be trained to acquire skills and experience for their job tasks so they can enhance their knowledge, solve problems, and communicate. Nowadays, integrating internships in higher education programs is one of the best practices that worldwide higher education institutes are offering. So, this Work-based capstone project has been studied based on the four areas of study to find out the improvement of the graduated alumni's professional development, professional skills, personal growth, and personal capabilities.

What more, the MNEC head office of central education department are who allocated the internship staffs, to be teachers at 136 Mon National School (MNS) at different village in Mon State, Tanintharyi Region and Karen State community. Additionally, the internship duty also takes place at office departments works at different units such as the administration unit, Finance unit, teacher education and Higher education unit, and broad-based capacity building for Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education support for material development, Research and Advocacy Unit, Monitoring and Evaluation Unit. The internship takes place at different department and school in office and school that administered by the Mon National Education Committee.

Since 2000, MNEC has started the institute of higher education, it was time when the internship program at Mon Post-ten school (formerly named of BHEEP) has started to increase the number of teaching human resources at the local community. The purpose of MNEC internship program was to fill the vacant teaching job positions in the field and in the office so BHEEP students will need to take two years internship as full-time teaching staff or office staffs in order to gain completion certificate. What more, Mon Community School students graduated were joining the MNEC higher education program but they had been learnt and passed grade by memorizing the information which is very few hands-on activities which made them difficult to work professionally right after high school graduates and also those who graduated from Myanmar country higher education Program or university.

Later, MNEC aims of this program is to enable students with the capacity to communicate clearly and professionally in 4 skills; reading, writing, listening and speaking English language, train up students to teach English to speaker of other language, and students will be able to apply the 21st century skills in problem solving, leadership and professional career. Students will be doing two-year internship to prepare for work readiness to enter to their suitable future career and further study. For this reason, this paper will analyze BHEEP internship to formulate strategic and examine the key factor to recommend clear evidence and principles of internship management and internship support programs for Mon Education Organization Leadership team to overcome resistance to change amongst their internship staff.

It is essential to identify if MNEC's higher education

program is providing hands-on learning activities to the students that can prepare them in professional and personal development, growth that support them to be ready for their future career. For this reason, some of these studies has identified a need to bring closer the Mon community and called for effective leading and managing the BHEEP internship programs under the direction of MNEC. This suggests that a better understanding must have been revealed by conducting researches on the existing internship program in BHEEP and developed effective internship support program of BHEEP internship program in MNEC is necessary. As such, this proposed research project aims to study the perception of internship participant for their job performance and opportunity for professional and personal development of BHEEP internship from MNEC support.

Section (2): Research Problem Identifications, Problem Statement, Research Aims and Objectives

Research Problem Identifications

There were about 500 BHEEP alumni who were graduated and has been completed the two-year internship program from the year of 2000 until recently. An internship is a short-term work of learning experience offered by companies and organizations for students to enter a specific work field as entry level such as doing a project, study about the work field to practice both hard and soft skills that can be approached to full-time job (Zhang, 2021) ^[21]. Graduates who have completed full-time, unpaid internships are just as likely to be employed or pursuing post-graduate education within one year following graduation, and have the same position and salary level as those who have been employed for five years who have been employed for five years (Saltikoff, 2017) ^[16].

Doing an internship is a learning that develops a work ethic, communication skills and ability to work on a team, polishing up students in reinforcing the institution rules and regulation and clarifying responsibilities is also helping students, mentors and employers understand their responsibility in an internship so students are confident in making decision in the career decision (J. Adams, 2013) ^[8].

For the organization which is not able to effort a lot of money like MNEC and it was in need of workers internship program is the best way to invite people to work in the organization to learn and help the business grow. Recruiting the right intern can have long-term benefits on your organization (Willoughby, 2014) ^[21]. Moran (2014) ^[13] listed 5 Beger's recommendations for creating a strong internship program such as (1) define the role of interns to complete their task, (2) train them with an orientation session for the internship, (3) appoint supervision who can answer questions and provide feedback, (4) stay compliant to teach them as many systems and processes to make sure not effecting the company or institute, (5) review regularly on intern feedback and evaluations. From Berger point of view it is essential to conduct a research on the MNEC existing internship services to know how much it is impacting in the graduated alumni professional growth, skills and personal development.

Designing an effective internship program will need to involve different factors to the program goal that is developed by the academic and community needs. MNEC must adapt to its environment that link with the local

community to assure the organization staffs support service available for every individual intern. Having specific roles and responsibilities, evaluating the organization's existing guidelines to support the internship, allowing interns to apply the classroom knowledge in real workplace, providing mandatory seminar and doing supervision and assessment of the interns are recommended in order to create effective internship program (Jackel, 2011) ^[9]. This study identified whether MNEC's internship programs offer opportunities to experience job skills, and soft skills, gain real-life experience, improve communication skills, and be supportive for their professional and personal development.

Problem Statement

Although there were different set of time period and course design, such research topic has not been conducted for the effectiveness of the internship program practice of BHEEP classroom, the internship program reported that being an intern teacher at Mon National School (MNS) is challenging and not improving their capacity for their future career because they believe their English skills have gone through their internship period. Again, the program report mentioned that most students do not plan to get a job at MNEC right after they complete their internship but the BHEEP internship program is one of the main sustainable human resource developments for MNEC (Soe, 2020) ^[17].

From the students' interns report, there isn't feedback channel for students to response and reach out to the organization so they didn't have enough support during their internship time. The internship program did not conduct the regular monitoring and evaluation trip to them although they need help in solving problems and need technical support for reflecting and learning through their internship period. There is needed to consider for some internship who has to stay at the location where there is no internet access, they might be having difficulty in learning new knowledge and lost their learning opportunity so it is needed to offer special chance to them for their professional development. Many internship staffs raise their voice in their monthly report that the internship opportunities do not reflect their goal of interest. As a result, the MNEC higher Education Program should have conducted research on the BHEEP internship program in order to support the program in getting the right guideline for instructional leadership and management by identifying the impact of internship program on the professional and personal development of Bop Htaw Education Empowerment Program (BHEEP) school graduates in MNEC.

Purpose and Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study is to determine how much the BHEEP internship program is beneficial for BHEEP students for their future career development, professional and personal growth. This study also aims to evaluate the impact of internship programs on the improvement of the professional and personal skills of BHEEP students after the completion of their internship period. The following objectives are set by the study in order to reach and achieve the purpose of the study;

Specific Objectives

- To study the background and rationale of engagement

of BHEEP students in internship programs.

- To study the impact of internship programs on professional as well as personal growth and skills of the BHEEP students and alumni.
- To identify the strengths and weaknesses of internship programs existing in MNEC.

Research Questions

- What is the knowledge background and rationale engagement of BHEEP students in internship programs at MNEC?
- What are the impacts of internship programs on professional as well as personal growth and skills of the BHEEP students and alumni?
- What are the strengths and weaknesses of the internship programs existing in MNEC? And how can it be improved to support the internship staff's professional growth and skills of the BHEEP alumni and future students?

Section (3) Selection and Application of Appropriate Techniques, Theories, tools and Practices to Addressing Research Problem(s) identified

Literature Review

The impact of internships on the personal development is increasing strong partnership with coworker, boosting individual confidence, morale and enhancing professional growth, promote efficiency, accountability and shipping learning theoretical knowledge in to real life is included. For this reason, experiencing internship support the holistic development of individuals, enhancing their personal and professional attributes simultaneously (Tupas, 2023) ^[18]. Educational organizations must provide effective professional development program which make space for students to applied in both business and education setting including update knowledge, seek for new skills, expand technology skills, research on management method, allocation idea through training and other development functions (Ruohotie, 1996) ^[14].

Hard skills mean the ability to do something in a field of working expert. For instance, conducting a research, design and implement projects, create curricula, and other. Likewise, soft skill such as working collaboratively, communication, critical thinking, building network, working under pressure, multitask working and able to learn new things are also important (Admin, 2022) ^[1]. Intern of professional skills development, both soft skills and hard skills are needed to enable individual career development. Personal development is a lifelong that guiding people to assess their individual skills to support in goal setting, decision making, reflection for awareness, and see direction life potential through learning and experiencing (Griffin, 2018) ^[5].

According to Loretto (2019) ^[12] internships are a proven way to gain relevant Knowledge, skills, experience and to identify a specific field recommendation for seeking a fulltime job. Running internship programmes for all courses in the TEL of Crete states that the extracurricular experiential learning practice provides real-life experiences to students, offer training, helps them identify long-term interests and goal, improve themselves, and above all improves their employability (Vairism Achilles and

Loulakakis, and petousis, 2013)^[3]. At first, MNEC aims to substitute teacher resources since internship has started in 2001 until now there was not any research that had conducted on the internship program yet so the program needed to be tested if the MNEC internship program is impacting on professional growth, skills and personal development.

Internship is a kind of learning tools but it doesn't guarantee of a job success. However, it is trained learner to boost their professional skills, experience learning opportunities for growth. Higher education around the world, especially in university internship program are highly integrated and it is a program that brightening students to the organizational partnerships to enhance their respective placements.

The internship types in MNEC is a kind of long period of time internship program which is needed time for two years to completed the internship period, only who completed the two year internship will earn the two year English Program learning certificate so there were two year learning in classroom and two more year training on job experience, in total four years learning. Fulltime. It also can be identified fulltime internship with monthly paid in the same pay role as other teacher and pre recruited staffs at where were placed at an internship staffs. Additionally, since MNEC is a non profit organization, there are different working field for such as administration field, teaching, technical and training unit, research, advocacy, and monitoring and evaluation, every year MNEC placed around 50 internships staffs at different working field.

Research Method and Design

This section of the study elaborates research methodology, data collection method, participants and sampling procedures, and data analysis techniques.

Research Methodology

Both quantitative and qualitative research has been used in this research to identify the following research hypothesis.

- H₁ MNEC's Internship programs have an impact on the professional development of the BHEEP graduated students.
- H₂ Internship programs have an impact on the professional skills of the BHEEP graduated students.
- H₃ Internship programs have an impact on the personal growth of the BHEEP graduated students.
- H₄ Internship programs have an impact on the personal capabilities of the BHEEP graduated students.

The four hypotheses have been studied through reviewing the program report, data and internship staffs report. Next, there was an online survey questionnaire delivering to volunteer for two months' time for them to fill out the survey questionnaire. The method also includes the focus group discussion and interviews to the internship alumni. What more, data analysis on the four parts of hypothesis and research questions was also conducted by the SPSS software to translated data. However, the rational background of the BHEEP internship program is also should be explored to have better comprehensive strengths and weaknesses of the internship program at MNEC as part of qualitative research through focus group discussion of random selected participants from the internship alumni, and some

qualitative research articles were also utilized in the literature review section.

Data Collection Method

This study data sources were a primary data source. The study has collected primary data from a maximum 51 BHEEP internship alumni from the academic year of 2014 to 2022 who graduated from BHEEP school, who are doing internship or completed internship for two years at MNEC and working both in MNEC and other private sectors in Mon Community. The survey questions were developed based on the following questions in order to send out to research participant to fill up and respond their answer (Appendices:1 survey questionnaires). The data was collected from May to June 2023 and questionnaires were distributed comprising of Part I: demographic information, Part II: reasons for participation in internship, Part III: Professional development, Part IV: professional skills and Part V: personal growth. The questionnaires was sent out through physically and electronically. Each variable of the questionnaire was assessed using 4-point Likert scale, they were strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), agree (3) and strongly agree (4). The questionnaires were distributed and collected both physically and electronically 43 closed-ended questionnaire items. There were 3 focus group discussion for qualitative (Appendix-2) has been interviews 10 participants.

Research Participants and Sampling

The participants were 51 BHEEP alumni who has graduated from BHEEP program from the academic year of 2014 to 2022. Those mentioned participants were who undergoing two years English program of BHEEP and who has taken internship at MNEC's internship program. For this study, Random convenient sampling is used as only the BHEEP alumni from 2015 to 2022. There are 37 females and 14 males, if show in percentage 72% of females and 27% males who had participated in answering the survey questions. They are located at different places around Mon state, some still working at Mon National School as teachers, some at MNEC offices as fulltime staffs and some of them are working at local educational institution and some at NGOs. For this study, Random convenient sampling is used as only who has join the BHEEP program from the academic of 2014 to 2022. What more, the process of this study has been working closely in getting contact and cooperate with MNEC higher education program staff to get great research for future MNEC higher education program.

Q.3 Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	female	37	72.5	72.5	72.5
	male	14	27.5	27.5	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

Data Analysis Techniques

This study has used frequency and percentage as a data analysis presentation of the survey questionnaire from the 51 volunteers' participants and focus group discussion. The evaluation of data involved in both descriptive and statistical analysis from the SPSS software to evaluate the

impact of internship programs on the professional, and personal growth and skills of the BHEEP graduated students and alumni. Descriptive technique of this study involved percentage and frequency analysis of demographic characteristics of the participants and central tendency measurement of their response, whereas statistical technique comprised of scale analysis including normality and reliability tests.

The reliability of the questionnaire was tested using Cronbach's alpha, and normality was evaluated employing univariate and multivariate normality of skewness and kurtosis. Structured questionnaire technique was used, comprising of six parts as mention in data analysis techniques. Results of this section contains the observation on findings and their estimations. This section has divided

into two parts, i.e., descriptive analysis and scale analysis. Descriptive analysis This section highlights the demographic characteristics of the respondents and central tendency measurement of their responses. Specifically presented percentage and frequency analysis of the study result in the below section (4). Appendices are attached for the detail survey questionnaire, and focus group discussion questions.

Section (4): Presentation of Analysis and Findings

This section of the study elaborates the findings of qualitative study on two parts of the questionnaire, i.e., demographic information and reasons for participation in the MNEC two-year internship program.

Table 1: Percentage and frequency distribution on demographic characteristics

Item	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender		
female	37	72.55
male	14	27.45
Age		
18 - 20	6	11.76
21 - 24	26	50.98
25 - 28	16	31.37
29 - 32	2	3.92
33 - 36	1	1.96
Academic Year		
1. 2014-2015	3	5.88
2. 2015 - 2016	6	11.76
3. 2016 - 2017	1	1.96
4. 2017 - 2018	2	3.92
5. 2018 - 2019	6	11.76
6. 2019 - 2020	19	37.25
7. 2020 - 2021	14	27.45
Education Level		
Finished high school	4	7.84
Graduated	11	21.57
Studying at a university	36	70.59
Job Title as an Internship		
Accountant	1	1.96
Admin staff	1	1.96
Database assistant	1	1.96
English Language Teacher	2	3.92
Health Education	1	1.96
Internship	2	3.92
Logistic	1	1.96
office staff	1	1.96
Office staff	3	5.88
Teacher	38	74.51
Length of internship experience		
1 year	13	25.49
2 years	36	70.59
3 years	2	3.92

Tables 1 and 2 indicate the findings. The results show that among 51 respondents, 37(72%) were females and 14 (27%) were males. In this study there were different ages range participated such as 6(11.76%) are from 18 to 20 years of age, 26 (50.98%) were from 21 to 24, 16 (31.37%) were from 25 to 28, 2(3.92%) were from 29 to 32 and 1(1.96%) was from 33 to 36 years of ages. They were from the different BHEEP academic year either as mentioned in table (1), 3 (5.88%) were 2014-2015, 6(11.76%) were 2015-2016,

1 (1.96%) were 2016-2017, 2 (3.92%) were 2017-2018, 6 (11.76%) were 2018-2019, 19 (37.25%) were 2019-2020, 14(27.45%) were 2020-2021. 4(7.84%) were who finished high school, 11(21.57%) were University graduate, and 36(70.59%) were who are still studying at university. Their job title as an internship were in different field as shown in the table. There were 1(1.96%) accountant, 1 (1.96%) admin staffs, 1(1.96%) databased assistance, 2(3.96%) English language teachers, 1(1.96%) heath education, 2(3.92%)

internship staffs, 1(1.96%) logistic, 4 (7.84%) office staffs, and teachers 38 (74.51%). The length of their internship

experience was 13(25.49%) of them 1 year, 36 (70.59%) of them 2 years and 2(3.92%) of them were 3 years.

Table 2: Percentage and frequency distribution of reasons for participation in internship

Item	Frequency	Percent
Reason for participating in the MNEC internship program		
a. requirement of the BHEEP academic discipline to get a certificate.	13	25.5
a. requirement of the BHEEP academic discipline to get a certificate., b. Own decision to gain experience	9	17.6
b. Own decision to gain experience	28	54.9
b. Own decision to gain experience, c. Recommended by family or supervisor expectation from the MNEC internship program	1	2.0
(a) Academic credit	4	7.8
(a) Academic credit, (b) Link classroom learning to real workplace	1	2.0
(a) Academic credit, (b) Link classroom learning to real workplace, (c) Gain a deeper understanding of suitable career direction	2	3.9
(a) Academic credit, (b) Link classroom learning to real workplace, (c) Gain a deeper understanding of suitable career direction, to work with the different types of people in big community which is based on Mon Culture	1	2.0
(a) Academic credit, (c) Gain a deeper understanding of suitable career direction	2	3.9
(b) Link classroom learning to real workplace	12	23.5
(b) Link classroom learning to real workplace, (c) Gain a deeper understanding of suitable career direction	6	11.8
(c) Gain a deeper understanding of suitable career direction	22	43.1
to improve my skills that I have learned for two years interested in the field of teaching/education field	1	2.0
No	14	27.5
Yes.	37	72.5
influence on obtaining current job		
No	3	5.9
Yes	48	94.1
influence upon future job promotions		
No	4	7.8
Yes	47	92.2
important of organizational award to internship staffs		
No	2	3.9
Yes	49	96.1
receive organization awards as an intern?		
No	24	47.1
Yes	27	52.9
awareness of two-year internship will need to be taken after two years of studied at BHEEP		
No	7	13.7
Yes	44	86.3

In table 2, it has shown the percentage and frequency distribution of reasons for participant in internship program. 13 (25.5%) participated in the MNEC internship program because they believed it is a requirement of the BHEEP academic discipline to get a certificate, 9(17.6%) of them believe it is a requirement of the BHEEP academic discipline to get a certificate and also, they make their own decision to gain experience, 28(54.9%) of them make their own decision to gain experience. 1(2%) said that it was their own decision and recommended by family or supervisor to participate in the internship program. 4 (7.8%) expected they will gain academic credit from the MNEC internship program, 1(2%) added that they believed the internship can link the knowledge that they have learnt from classroom to real workplace and gain deeper understanding of suitable career direction, another 1(2%) aims also can work with different types of people in wider community which is based on Mon culture. 2(3.9%) of them reasoned that they can get academic credit and gain a deeper understanding of suitable career direction and link the classroom knowledge to real workplace. 12(23.5%) believed they can only link the knowledge that they had learnt from the classroom to the real workplace. 6(11.8%) aims to link classroom learning to real workplace and gain deeper understanding of suitable career direction, 22 (43.1%) of them wanted to gain a deeper understanding of suitable career direction, and 1(2%) want to improve their skills that they have learnt for two years at BHEEP.

Among all the participants 14(27.5%) of them said they were not interested in the field of teaching and education but 37(72%) of them mentioned that they were interested in teaching and education field so the skewness of this point fall to "yes" which mean the internship program provided internship opportunities with the right interest of the students and organization provided useful job opportunities to the internship staffs. Only 3(5.9%) rejected that the internship experience does not influence their current job but 37(94%) of them said that their internship has big impacted on the current job and 47(92%) of them also agreed that the internship experience will support their future job promotions when there were 3(5.9%) of them does not see it is influencing their future job career, 49(96%) said that the organizational award is important to the internship staffs to be motivated and 24(47.1%) of them have never received an awards as an intern and 27(52.9%) of them received organization awards as an intern which was help them to be motivated in trying to accomplished the two year internship program. Finally, most of them 44(86%) of them were aware of two-year internship will need to be taken after two years of studies at BHEEP but there are a few of them 7(13.7%) of them did not.

Measurement of central tendencies

This part deals with the findings of mean and standard deviation for the items of part III to Part VI of the questionnaire. Table 3 show the results.

Table 3: Measurement of central tendencies

Variables	Items	Means	Standard Deviation (SD)
Professional development (PD)	PD1	3.14	0.491
	PD2	2.86	0.722
	PD3	3.31	0.761
	PD4	3.12	0.588
	PD5	3.22	0.577
	PD6	2.94	0.705
Professional Skills (PS)	PS1	3.47	0.612
	PS2	3.20	0.491
	PS3	3.45	0.642
	PS4	3.16	0.579
	PS5	2.90	0.806
	PS6	3.20	0.633
Professional Growth (PG)	PG1	3.20	0.530
	PG2	2.73	0.603
	PG3	2.94	0.645
	PG4	3.10	0.500
	PG5	3.04	0.564
	PG6	2.96	0.488
Professional Capabilities (PC)	PC1	3.18	0.518
	PC2	3.27	0.493
	PC3	3.37	0.692
	PC4	3.39	0.666
	PC5	3.31	0.678
	PC6	3.10	0.539

These results showed central tendencies of the responses for all the items of part III to part VI of the questionnaire by the 51 participants of the study. The highest mean and highest standard deviation (SD) for professional development (PD) are 3.31 and 0.761, the lowest mean and lowest SD for PD are 2.86 and 0.491 respectively. The range of mean 2.86 – 3.31 depicts that response of BHEEP alumni are moving from “disagree” to “agree” for all the items of PD. The lowest and highest means for professional skills (PS) are 2.90 and 3.47, while the lowest SD and highest SD are 0.491 and 0.806, respectively. The mean range 2.90 and

3.47 moving from “disagree” to “agree” of BHEEP alumni for all the items of PS. The lowest mean and lowest SD for personal growth (PG) are 2.73 and 0.488, whereas the highest mean and highest SD are 3.20 and 0.806, respectively. The mean range 2.73 – 3.20 indicates that BHEEP alumni moving from “disagree” to “agreed” with all the items of PG. The lowest and highest means for personal capabilities (PC) are 3.10 and 3.39, the while lowest SD and highest SD are 0.493 and 0.692, respectively. The mean range 3.10–3.39 shows “agree” which it positive responses of BHEEP alumni for all the items of PC.

Table 4: Skewness and Kurtosis test

Variables	Items	Kurtosis	Skewness
Professional development (PD)	PD1	0.923	0.337
	PD2	0.434	-0.451
	PD3	1.616	-1.172
	PD4	-0.052	-0.019
	PD5	-0.236	-0.029
	PD6	1.019	-0.631
Professional Skills (PS)	PS1	3.333	-1.248
	PS2	0.374	0.446
	PS3	2.619	-1.224
	PS4	-0.063	-0.008
	PS5	-0.403	-0.293
	PS6	1.825	-0.670
Professional Growth (PG)	PG1	0.135	0.190
	PG2	0.423	-0.380
	PG3	0.883	-0.412
	PG4	6.224	-0.786
	PG5	3.211	-0.681
	PG6	1.491	-0.106
Professional Capabilities (PC)	PC1	0.353	0.243
	PC2	-0.521	0.509
	PC3	1.392	-1.030
	PC4	1.876	-1.069
	PC5	1.349	-0.882
	PC6	0.531	0.091

Scale measurement

This section elaborates normality and reliability tests results, evaluated to check the normality of distribution of the data of the study and reliability of the questionnaire.

Multivariate normality test

A perfect normal distribution with acceptable skewness range is ± 3 (Yenigun, 2023) [22] with acceptable kurtosis range of ± 7 (Good Data, 2021) [4]. The data of this study will be normally distributed of values of kurtosis and skewness fall with this range. the result is shown in table (4) of the questionnaire. The findings indicated that the critical values of skewness range from -1.248 (PS1) to 0.509 (PC2) whereas critical values of kurtosis range from -0.531(PC2) to 6.224 (PG4). The result directed that all the values of Skewness and Kurtosis fall between the acceptable rage so the data of this study were normally distributed.

Reliability tests

The reliability of the questionnaire is checked by using Cornbach's coefficient alpha. According to the S. Taber (2017) [15], the questionnaire is reliable if the Cronbach's coefficient alpha is above 0.70. the result of this finding is Showen in the table (5) and represent the values of Cronbach's coefficient alpha range from 0.708 to 0.798, the values fall in acceptable range so the questionnaire of the study is reliable.

Table 5: Reliability analysis

Variables	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Professional Development	6	0.769
Professional Skills	6	0.745
Professional Growth	6	0.708
Professional Capabilities	6	0.798

Qualitative study Report

Three focus group discussion (FGD) were conducted, two FGDs involved 3 participants and four participated in one FGD. The 10 participants randomly selected from who had experienced in teaching, in office field and both, and they been studied from 2014 to 2022. There were 4 internship teachers, 4 office staffs, and 2 of them experienced both as teacher and office staff. Those who worked at office had taken role as accountant, admin staffs, database assistance, health education staffs, internship staff, and logistic. The teacher's interns were located at different MNS, BHEEP, and Mon Youth Education Development (MYED) program. They decided to join the internship program because they want to full fill the BHEEP program, also want to be more responsible and gain more experience to link the knowledge that they have learnt from their classroom experience. Form the Focus group discussion of survey participants (n=9, 90%) of them were satisfied with their internship experience that they had done but (n=1, 1%) of them need to do even though they don't like it. For instance, while student's teacher had don't their teaching practicum at their classroom project, their supervisor suggested them to teach middle school classes but the internship position assigned them to teach at primary school children so they faced problem in dealing with small children. And (n=2, 20%) of them did not aware that they had to do two-year internship after they have study two-year English program at BHEEP.

Internship made them able to apply the skill that they learn from the classroom (IT, computer and other soft skills such as communication, creativity, collaboration), improved English skills that they had learnt from the school and useable in the workplace, in daily life and career. As data shown in table 2 most of them interest in education field but some didn't. In order to have deeper explore more reasons on this, the FGD result informed that this might be because of their field of experience not support their future career, as they do not want to keep working as teachers, and they have another field of interest rather than education and teaching. Most of them (n = 48%, 94%) obtaining current job, (n= 47%, 92%) influence their future career because of internship impact but only a few of them (n= 3, 6%) response not.

In this study there are four parts that mainly studied and analysis, they are professional development, professional skills, professional growth and professional capability. Participants (n=8, 80%) response that the internship program changes their professionally because they have experienced in dealing with different people at the community, work collaboratively, practice to do decision, increase social and communication skills.

A FGD answered that "We work collaboratively and engagement skills with internal and external partner, we learn to discipline with the role and responsibility, eg.; take responsibility in keeping the resources, and share what is need."

An intern said "At first I want to be a teacher before doing internship, when I really work and in tough with office staffs (being a training organizer) it helps me to be cleared in identifying the field that I am interested".

The interview result proved that the two-year internship time direct them to clearer goal as a few still need more time. Two teachers responded that they do not want to changes their career because they felt that are belong to the schools and had responsible for the children education at their village. Two of FGDs have seen their field of interest from the internship because can observe the working style, procedure and found their interest so they believed if they finished their internship they could be promoted and some of them were promoted to fulltime job such as data-based assistance, logistic, admin staffs, accountant and finance staffs and other. Interns' teacher (n=2, 20%) responded that they might stop from teaching because of their family income and needs but it will be hardly acceptable to stop working from the field of education, which they had experienced from internship to full time teacher many years. One of them (from FGDs discussion) still does not have clear goal and future career as they are still looking and learning from their work experience, although they finished their internship and promoting to a full-time job. Two of them responded that both teaching job and office staff were their interest as an intern because it can support my future career to have multiple job choices.

Firstly, all the 3 FGDs agreed that internship was practical learning, added new knowledge and skills except from what they have learnt at BHEEP class. For example, when they were students, they didn't own a computer to practice but as an intern, they had a chance to use computer, applied the language skills, applied teaching professional skills in real classroom with different student's background, improved

lesson plan writing skills, accounting skills, leading skills, time and work plan management, creativity and innovative in design thinking, and develop flexibility in work. During their internship, training and workshop also increasing their professional working skills. What more, it also advanced communication skills by dealing with school head teacher, co-worker, educational leaders from different township, work with other people. For instance, working as training organizer have to deal and communicate with trainers and educators to plan the training plan, also had a chance to expend wider network with external educator. As experience years were added, they learnt more about people behavior and accept the different attitude of different people. As an illustration, a teacher intern learns and aware of student background and needs which helped him a lot in lesson planning and choosing appropriate teaching method.

Those FGD are between 20 to 25 years of ages, so they were in the ages of stepping out of their parents gardant and getting in touch with real work life. They agreed that internship period was useful when they can upgrade their professional growth because they said they have to live and guide themselves, learnt to be strong and overcome life challenge. Financial management experience from both at work project and personal income and expend were usable for both their professional and personal. Some from them moving from careless to more careful in finishing the daily task. Working with other and finish the job task together make them have better time management and adopted positive habit from friends and senior staffs. In sum up they prefer to say that they were moving to more mature in both work and personal growth.

Internship experience directed their future goal and career they prefer. (n=4,40%) of them want to continue working as teacher, four of them aims to be promoted to higher position at office or program, when one respondent still needs more time to explore the field of their interest. From the two-year working as internship staffs, they learnt to reflect their self and changes to more positive wipe and able to make decision where to place to them in the field of the career that not only interest but also match with their capacity. In addition, they were confidence to lead somethings in both at work and personal life. Being flexibility, patient, accepting the different were also one of important things that they improve from the internship.

Section (5): Presentation of Solutions and Recommendations

Presentation of the Solutions

The Rationale Background Engagement of BHEEP Students in Internship Programs at MNEC: In this study, female (72%) and male (27%) participants has been participated the result of this study is mostly from the age of range between 21-24 (51%) and high number of participants from the academic year of 2019-2020, 2020-2021, some from 2015-2016, 2018-2019, and a few of them from 2014-2015, 2016-2017, and 2017-2018. Most of them had been taken internship as teachers, some of them were office staffs in different position as shown in table 1, and a few of them were taken as both teachers and office staff. Most of them decided to involved in the internship program because of their own decision, follow by because of it was a requirement of the BHEEP academic discipline to get a

certificate.

Most of them are still learning at university, some graduated and a few of them just finish high school, and most of them has compete 2 years length of internship, some of them has taken one year and still in the field of internship, a few of them are 3 years (who are promoted to full time staff or teacher). Based on this finding, it also could be analyzed to the range of ages and education background as most were from the range of ages between 21-24, university while they are still learning the theory concept, language, skills and developing personal development to identify a suitable career. The surveyors 71% response "yes" to the questions of interested in the field of teaching and education field, which is in line with the internship opportunities that MNEC has provided to BHEEP graduated. The result proved (94% of them response) that the internship program was influence on obtaining their current job.

From the finding, almost all them said it is essential to see the important of organizational award to internship staffs for the purpose of motivation, and 52% of them had been received organization award as intern which also responded in the focus group discussion that award made them motivate to keep doing best in their work and learn to seek new skills, felt belong to the organization, stimulated their attachment to continue working at MNEC job sectors. Among the 51 participants 86% of them were aware that two-year internship will need to be taken after two years of studies at BHEEP which means a few of them did not have any awareness of two-year internship will need to be taken so this result can be affected to some internship participant and the FGD also responded two-year period of them is quite long and difficult for them to continue their further learning and look for the right choice of career direction.

5.1.2 The Impact of Internship Programs

Different researchers proved that most educational institute offer internship program to provide practical experience through, and evaluate their practical experience to link the lesson that they have learn from the classroom in real workplace. What more, the discussion also mentioned that those who participated in internship knew their role and responsibility, confidence in decision making in both their professional and personal life.

This study participants replied that the internship links the classroom learning to real workplace (23%) and gain a deeper understanding of suitable career direction (43%), 94% participants responded that the internship influence on obtaining the current job, 92% replied it influenced upon future job promotions. Next, the questionnaire items of part III to part VI such as professional development (PD), Professional skills (PS), professional Growth (PG), and professional capabilities (PC) by the participants (n = 51) indicated the finding of the critical values of skewness range from -1.248 (PS1) to 0.509 (PC2) whereas critical values of kurtosis range from -0.531(PC2) to 6.224 (PG4) which defined the value of skewness and kurtosis fall between the acceptable range, and the Cronbach's coefficient alpha range from 0.708 to 0.798, which mean the value fall in acceptable range. For this reason, the result indicated that the internship program is having effective impact on professional as well as personal growth, and skills of the BHEEP graduated.

The Strengths and Weaknesses of the MNEC's Internship Programs

Strength of BHEEP graduated internship program

- (N=28, 54%) of participants suggest that they made their own decision to gain experience, (N=22, 43%) said that they had done their internship for deeper understanding of suitable career direction and (n=13,25%) of them has joined the internship program which was the requirement of the BHEEP academic discipline to get certificated.
- The field of internship that MNEC provided has been useful and impact to their current professional career and job promotion, as well as influencing their future career.
- Internship programs progressed internship students in professional development, skills, professional growth and professional capability.
- The organization aims to increase education field human resources and provide internship opportunities in different fields of work with the educational institute such as being a teacher at Mon National school, project/ program staffs with different positions which stimulated participants motivation to work the field where they can apply the skills that they learn from the classroom and seek more skills during internship period.
- This BHEEP two-year paid internship increased youth in the community to linkage their further job opportunity as well as seek for further study, and also increasing skillful human resources for different type of organizational and institution at the community.

Weaknesses and Areas that need to be improved for the more supportive of the internship program

- From the study (n=44, 86%) of them aware but there was still (n=7, 13.7%) of them didn't have awareness of two-year internship program. So, it can also define that the program didn't clearly inform to all of the students before they join the learning program that two years of internship will need to be taken after two years of studies at BHEEP.
- Before doing practicum, the internship opportunities should need to match and interest in internship field. For example, some want to teach but some want to experience as office staffs. Example; "I am working in admin field, but I want to work in M&E field and I don't gain chance to work in that field during my internship so I am not able to experience what M&E field in reality". Some has experience in teaching, want to join office work but does not gain experience and chance to know what need to do in office so they have less experience in applying MNEC job that has been announced so they stop working with MNEC.
- Doing internship in the same field for two years make them less motivated and less chance to learn from the other field that they think they are interesting and the period of two years is quite long for those who want to study. However, those who was taken in role that matched with the position does not have problem with the time and they continue working in the same field after they finished the internship time. For this reason, length of internship should be rearranged and plan to provide equal opportunities for internship participants.

- The organization should have system of monitoring and evaluation on the internship program participant and reinforcement for the rewarding the work accomplishment. From the study shown that (n = 49, 96.1%) participants said organizational award to internship staffs is important, and (n = 27, 52%) received organizational award and (n=24, 47%) had never received any award. For this reason, although half of them received organizational reward, the FGDs suggest it is better to keep regular monitoring and evaluation system together rewarding the internship staff on the work accomplishment because they believed it will keep them motivate in working, learning and promote happy working environment.

Recommendation

- The linkage between BHEEP curriculum should be matched with the internship field and needs of community human resources.
- The internship professional development trainings were also being suggested to be provided for different field of working interns so everyone could develop their professional capacity in the field where they are placing.
- In addition, workplace internship supervisor should allow the intern to join their internship professional development activity.
- The internship program should be systematic monitor and evaluate and regular responsive to their suggestion and feedback on their strength and weakness during their internship period.
- This study is proved that in internship program encourage the BHEEP students in gaining deeper experimental knowledge from real workplace which can be easily promoted to full time job and best choice of future career. This result also will help the MNEC higher education program to consider skills that needed for integrating in the higher education program curricula.
- Providing the internship opportunity will help skillful youth to understand to the organization and maintain qualified staffs for longer period and improve human resources management system in MNEC.
- What more, the rewarding system to the internship program participants is also having big impact to both professional and personal development as well as working performance to completed work task.
- Internship program benefit to both organization and those who join internship in positive impact of the professional development and personal development. By providing internship program to the higher education graduated students, it also reduced the organization recruitment and new staff training cost to hider new employee.
- The program can do more study on exploring different internship program at different institutions and different country.

It can be concluded that MNEC aims to strengthen human resource development through the BHEEP internship programs by preparing students to be ready for their career and professional job. Analysis of this study based on the

51 volunteers from the BHEEP's academic year 2014 to 2022. The study mainly analysis the six parts such as demographic information; reasons for participation in internship, evaluation of information regarding professional and personal growth and skills improvement of the BHEEP graduated students, including the 3FGDs.

- Firstly, this study has identified that 72% of the internship participants were interested in education field which is a positive impact for MNEC in trying to makes changes and sustainable development of educational human resources from this internship program. 94% agreed that the internship influence on obtaining the current job, 92% of internship alumni had positive attitude that the internship program is influencing upon their future career and job promotion.
- Secondly, MNEC's Internship programs have effective impacts on both the professional and personal development for the BHEEP graduated students. The range of mean 2.86 – 3.31 depicts that response of BHEEP alumni are moving from “disagree” to “agree” for all the items of PD which can be defined that internship programs have positive impact on the professional development of the BHEEP graduated. The mean range 2.90 and 3.47 moving from “disagree” to “agree” of BHEEP alumni for all the items of PS which can be defined that Internship programs also have impact on the personal Skills of the BHEEP graduated students. The mean range 2.73 – 3.20 indicates that BHEEP alumni moving from “disagree” to “agreed” with all the items of PG which mean that Internship programs have an impact on the personal Growth of the BHEEP graduated students. The mean range 3.10–3.39 shows “agree” which its positive responses of BHEEP alumni for all the items of PC which mean the internship program have positive impact on the Professional Capabilities.
- Thirdly, students made their own decision to join the internship in order to have clear direction for their future career, to apply knowledge and skills that had learnt from the classroom. And the field of internship were useful for obtaining their current job and future. Additionally, different working positions at an educational institution (MNEC) were given chance for student to choose the field of their interest in doing internship. Students became interested in education field as an intern staff so they decided to keep working at MNEC as a teacher or office staffs in different position.
- However, the internship program should be informed about the two-year internship to every single student who is going to study at the higher education program. Field of internship position should be matched with students' field of interest and field of their study at the higher education program. What more, regular monitoring and evaluation of the internship staffs should be implemented systematically, supporting on the internship capacity development, and rewarding system should be integrated systematically so they will be motivated to participated and stimulated their mind to keep working at MNEC.

In conclusion, the different type of internships has different impact on both institution and participants of the internship program. The organization should consider and established characteristic of effective internship program to link with MNEC higher education program and internship opportunities based on both need to students and communities. Internship program is benefit and have positive impact of internship participation for both professional and personal development, together with the recommendation and suggestions on the areas of internship program's improvement that prepare work readiness and increase skillful youth in the community to take role on the working area of community development in the field of providing quality education in southern Myanmar, Mon State.

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